

AESTHETIC DENTISTRY AND ITS HISTORICAL EVOLUTION

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Summary. The paper studies visual appeal dental science as an independent field with its own history of advancement, theoretical basis, also presents the stages of advancement of visual appeal dental science in historical aspect, describes odontological parameters, history of teeth whitening, qualitative characteristics of dental color, stages of advancement of filling substances, visual appeal constructions.

Keywords: color formation, fillings, teeth whitening, visual appeal designs, visual appeal dental science.

The active advancement of technical means and substances science for dental science has determined the rapid introduction of new clinical methods for the restoration of teeth and dentition defects. The high efficiency of visual appeal structures turned out to be attractive to patients, which stimulated most dentists to master and use modern substances in practice, primarily light-curing composites. In the current situation of mass use of photopolymers, as well as various auxiliary means, devices, devices, the shortage of basic theoretical and scientific knowledge in the field of shape formation and color science becomes noticeable. The separation of visual appeal dental science into a separate branch of dental science and practice allows us to increase the level of theoretical training and practical skills of specialists working in the field of visual appeal restoration.

Historical aspects of the advancement of visual appeal dental science. The advancement of visual appeal dental science is closely related to the history of mankind. Anatomists, artists, sculptors and doctors sought to measure the human body and face and find their optimal proportions. Thanks to this, canons began to appear (literally "prescription") - a set of artistic techniques or rules. Each canon was based on a module - the size of any part of the human body or face. In Egyptian art, the module was the distance from the sole to the ankle of the leg, in ancient Greek it was the height of the head, and the length of the body was an eightfold increase in the module. According to the canon of Polykleitos of Sikyon, corresponding to the modern term "physiognomic height of the face," in a harmoniously developed body, the height of the face should be 10 times. In the statues created by Lysippos, the height of the face was placed 9 times, and the height of the body was equal to the distance between the ends of the fingers of outstretched hands. This ratio is called the "square of the ancients."

In modern conditions, Nacagawa and Yamamoto have proposed ways to assess the color and transparency of dental tissues. E.A.Hegenbart, Ch.Gran described the differences between

dental enamel and ceramic substances. Adrian et al. studied the correspondence of the color of substances to their standards. G. Ubassi, based on the theory of the optical properties of enamel, developed recommendations for dental technicians.

Throughout the history of society, pearly white teeth have been considered an integral part of human beauty.

In the literature there are tips on teeth whitening for certain types of pigmentation. Thus, I.G. Lukomsky (1960) recommended removing dense colored plaque by scraping with an excavator, machine cleaning with a brush with pumice and hydrogen peroxide. It was recommended to remove smoker's plaque using iodine tincture, hydrogen peroxide, pumice, and also machine brushing of teeth. Pigmentation due to fluorosis was eliminated by applying decalcifying agents to the dental crown. E.V. Borovsky (1973) described a whitening method by exposing the enamel to a saturated solution of organic acids (citric, tartaric) or a 10% solution of hydrochloric acid until pigmentation disappears. After this, the dental is treated with soda paste and polished with a composition of pumice or phosphate cement powder mixed with glycerin. T.F. Vinogradova proposed a method for lightening "tetracycline stains" with hydrogen peroxide, hydroperite, and perhydrol. Nonspecific systemic hypoplasia was subjected to remineralization therapy followed by fluoride varnish coating. For hypoplasia of the incisal edge, gradual grinding of the enamel in small portions with remineralizing therapy after each preparation was recommended.

In the late 1980s, Haywood and Heyman introduced the technique of "dentist-prescribed, patient-administered overnight, intravital safe whitening." The American Dental Association (ADA) in the 90s proposed a program for the advancement and use of substances containing hydrogen peroxide in the form of three types of dental products: commercial antiseptics; bleaches, usually containing 3% hydrogen peroxide (10% carbamide peroxide); dental pastes (powders) with low concentrations of hydrogen peroxide or calcium hydroxide.

The population's demand for teeth whitening has increased significantly in recent years. At the same time, the number of doctors recommending vital whitening is increasing.

Shape formation and color science as a theoretical basis for visual appeal dental science. One of the main concepts of modern dental science is the visual appeal function of the dental. It implies harmony of size, shape, relief, position of the dental in the arch; optical properties of dental tissues, including a special range of color shades, fluorescence, opalescence and gloss of enamel.

Mathematical terms are used to describe the anatomical characteristics of a dental. Surfaces are compared to flat geometric figures, and shapes and relief are compared to volumetric bodies. Flat figures are formed by points located on the same plane. A circle is defined as a set of points on a plane that are equidistant from the center. An oval is an elongated circle, and a regular oval is an ellipse.

Plane figures with angles are polygons: triangles, quadrangles, etc. A quadrilateral with two pairs of parallel sides is a parallelogram, which is considered a rectangle if all its angles are right angles. A square is a rectangle with all sides equal.

Even a minimum of knowledge in the field of mathematics allows us to describe the basic geometric shapes of dental surfaces as flat figures. In rectangular teeth, the transverse dimensions of the vestibular surface in the gingival, equatorial region and at the cutting edge are close in value. The lateral surfaces are almost parallel, the length of contact with adjacent teeth is significant.

With a triangular crown, the transverse dimensions of the vestibular surface increase from the neck to the cutting edge: the crown expands. The proximal surfaces diverge. Contacts between teeth are point-like. The oval shape of the crown is characterized by close values of the transverse dimensions of the vestibular surface in the cervical region and near the cutting edge. The largest diameter is in the equator region. The proximal surfaces appear in the form of convex arcs, with point contacts with adjacent teeth.

The visual perception of the geometric shape of a dental can be influenced by its individual characteristics. The dome-shaped gingival margin, characteristic of 56% of incisors, resembles a wedge or triangle in shape. 39% of crowns have a rounded periodontal edge, 5% have a flattened, almost straight contour. The shape of the cutting edge can be smooth, convex, concave, embossed.

Teeth, being three-dimensional bodies, have spatial characteristics: height, thickness, width, relief. An example of geometric three-dimensional figures (the latter are studied by the branch of mathematics - stereometry) are polyhedra. In particular, a straight prism represents a body enclosed between parallel polygons. A triangular right prism has triangles as its bases. If the base is a rectangle, then it is a rectangular parallelepiped. If all sides are equal, it is a cube.

The pyramid also represents a three-dimensional body. At its base is a polygon, the vertices of which are connected to one point lying outside this plane.

A cylinder is obtained by rotating a rectangle around one of its sides. A cone is formed by rotating a right triangle around one of its legs. The ball can be obtained by rotating a semicircle around its diameter. A cross section of a ball with any plane will result in a circle.

Description of the shape of teeth is difficult due to the presence of protrusions, depressions, and roughness on its surface. However, upon careful analysis, one can detect sections that are close in shape to a cylinder (in the cervical region), a cone (in the area of masticatory teeth tubercles), and a flattened prism (in the area of the incisal edge). In accordance with this, all teeth are divided into groups that differ in the shape of the crown: spade-shaped (incisors), cone-shaped (fangs), cylindrical double-tubercular (small molars - premolars), cylindrical multi-tubercular (large molars - molars).

The relief also has three-dimensional characteristics. For example, the central incisors of the upper jaw of young people are characterized by a vestibular surface with vertical enamel ridges. In the lateral incisors, the median enamel ridge usually predominates in height, which in the canines turns into a more convex tubercle.

Description of the optical characteristics of a dental also requires the use of special terms and concepts. An integral understanding of the laws of formation and perception of color is given by color science, which includes sections of physics (optics), physiology and psychology (vision), painting theory, and philosophy.

The patterns of refraction of light rays explain the appearance of color. Since the angle of refraction depends on the wavelength, or color, of the beam, when passing through a prism, white light undergoes decomposition into the colors of the rainbow (the phenomenon of dispersion).

In physics (optics), it is customary to place all colors on the same straight line in accordance with the wavelength (from red to violet). In color science, they are arranged in a circle: contrasting colors are located opposite each other. The sequence of tones in any color wheel is the same, the number is no more than 160 (the limit of discrimination by the eye).

The most trained observers are able to distinguish 150 shades by color tones, 25 by saturation, and up to 64 by lightness.

The qualitative characteristics of dental color can also be tone, lightness, and saturation. Visually perceived tones, or shades, can be described as white, yellow, gray, blue, brown. By lightness they are characterized as follows: yellow - varies; gray, blue - come in light colors; brown - very light. The following gradations can be distinguished by saturation: yellow tones - vary; gray and blue are characterized by low saturation, brown shades are characterized by very low saturation.

The main shades of a dental are explained by the characteristics of the structure and composition of the dental. Thus, the maximum reflection of all colored rays by the surface, as well as the scattering abilities of the enamel, determine the white color. In addition, having a tendency to internally scatter light, enamel imparts blue shades to the color scheme, as well as the ability to opalescent.

The color of dentin is revealed due to the light transmission of enamel. The incisal area does not have dentin, so it appears more transparent. The middle part of the dental often contains the bulk of yellowish dentin, which determines the color of the dental as a whole. The cervical area of the dental has a thinner layer of enamel, so the color of the underlying dentin is more clearly expressed.

Age-related differences in the optical properties of a dental can be presented as follows. A young dental with its surface reflects more light than a mature one, while having a high scattering ability. Its dentin contains less pigments. As a result, white color predominates in the reflection spectrum. A mature dental is characterized by a reduced scattering ability of the enamel and an increase in the selective reflection of dentin, which forms the inherent shade of the dental. The layer of dentin exposed as a result of physiological abrasion of teeth gives the cutting edge a dark yellowish, brownish tint. In addition, the color of sclerotic and secondary dentin is often yellow-brown. Darkening is enhanced by pigments that easily penetrate exposed dentin.

In ensuring the visual appeal function, the phenomenon of irradiation is important - the influence of color on the visual perception of the volumetric parameters of the dental. Thus, warm colors (yellow - orange) seem to protrude, while cold colors (blue) recede into the depths.

Since dental structures must imitate living teeth in tone, saturation, and lightness, dentists must have knowledge in the field of shape formation and color science.

The rapid acquisition by specialists of manual skills in the field of visual appeal dental science is ahead of their acquisition of theoretical knowledge and scientifically based recommendations, including due to the insufficient supply of special educational, scientific and methodological literature. At the same time, the accumulated world experience indicates that there is a need to develop and formulate basic concepts, provisions, and definitions of visual appeal dental science as a science that ensures the widespread implementation of the proposed means and methods in practical healthcare.

Thus, an analysis of literary sources and work experience shows the urgent need to define visual appeal dental science as an independent field that has its own history of advancement and theoretical basis. The improvement of substances, equipment, and accessories for dental science had a significant impact on its advancement. The practical use of advanced methods of treating

caries and non-carious lesions of teeth allows us to ensure high quality of modern work such as restoration, reconstruction, adhesive prosthetics, splinting using photopolymerizing substances.

In Uzbekistan, the history of the evolution of dental science as a separate science began in 1954, when the dental faculty of the Tashkent Medical Institute was opened. The Institute was established by the Decree of the President «On the formation of the Tashkent State Dental Institute» dated July 22, 2014, on the basis of the Faculty of Dentistry of the Tashkent Medical Academy. Now the Institute has five faculties - the Faculty of Dentistry, the Faculty of Pediatric Dentistry, the Faculty of Medicine and Education, the Faculty of Medicine and the Faculty of Advanced Studies. Faculties of dental science are also available in other medical universities of the republic. Since 2009, the Faculty of Dentistry has been opened at the Samarkand State Medical Institute.

Looking back and returning to the past stages of evolution of dental care in Uzbekistan, we can note a steady movement forward. Each stage of the evolution of specialized care had its own characteristics and difficulties. Overcoming them, dental care to the population of the republic grew stronger, grew, and developed. The rapid evolution of technology since the beginning of the 20th century has led to the emergence of new methods and materials that have begun to be used in dental science. Summing up, we note that the historical experience of the evolution of dental care should not be forgotten in the context of reforming the health care of the republic.

The evolution of precision casting and milling technologies has made it possible to create comfortable and durable clasp prostheses. Ceramic restorations are widely used, allowing you to accurately repeat the natural shape and color. A real revolution in prosthetics was the method of implantation, especially important in the case of complete absence of teeth. Scientific and technological progress today has given us such opportunities that even 100 years ago would have seemed like a miracle, and it does not stop for a minute. Looking at the emerging new technologies, such as 3D printing, one can only guess what dental science will become already in the near future.

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